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CLASS D POWER AMPLIFIER FOR MEDICAL APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this research was to design a 2.4 GHz class AB Power Amplifier (PA), with 0.18um Semiconductor Manufacturing International Corporation (SMIC) CMOS technology by using Cadence software, for health care applications. The ultimate goal for such application is to minimize the trade-offs between performance and cost, and between performance and low power consumption design. This paper introduces the design of a 2.4GHz class D power amplifier which consists of two stage amplifiers. This power amplifier can transmit 15dBm output power to a 50Ω load. The power added efficiency was 50% and the total power consumption was 90.4 mW. The performance of the power amplifier meets the specification requirements of the desired.

KEYWORDS

Two stage, Class D, Power amplifier, Healthcare

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HOSOYA POLYNOMIAL, WIENER AND HYPERWIENER INDICES OF SOME REGULAR GRAPHS

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ABSTRACT

Let G be a graph. The distance $d(u,v)$ between two vertices u and v of G is equal to the length of a shortest path that connects u and v . The Wiener index $W(G)$ is the sum of all distances between vertices of G , whereas the hyper-Wiener index $WW(G)$ is defined as $WW(G) = \sum_{\{u,v\} \subseteq V(G)} (d(u,v) + d(v,u))$. Also, the Hosoya polynomial was introduced by H. Hosoya and define $h(G, x) = \sum_{\{u,v\} \subseteq V(G)} x^{d(u,v)}$. In this paper, the Hosoya polynomial, Wiener index and Hyper-Wiener index of some regular graphs are determined.

KEYWORDS

Network Protocols, Topological distance, Hosoya polynomial, Wiener Index, Hyper-Wiener index, Regular graph, Harary graph

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FACE RECOGNITION: A SURVEY SHAILAJA A PATIL¹ AND DR. P. J. DEORE²

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ABSTRACT

Face Recognition plays a major role in Biometrics. Feature selection is a measure issue in face recognition. This paper proposes a survey on face recognition. There are many methods to extract face features. In some advanced methods it can be extracted faster in a single scan through the raw image and lie in a lower dimensional space, but still retaining facial information efficiently. The methods which are used to extract features are robust to low-resolution images. The method is a trainable system for selecting face features. After the feature selection procedure next procedure is matching for face recognition. The recognition accuracy is increased by advanced methods.

KEYWORDS

Face features, feature selection, local binary pattern.

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LOW POWER SI CLASS E POWER AMPLIFIER AND RF SWITCH FOR HEALTH CARE

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ABSTRACT

This research was to design a 2.4 GHz class E Power Amplifier (PA) for health care, with 0.18um Semiconductor Manufacturing International Corporation CMOS technology by using Cadence software. And also RF switch was designed at cadence software with power Jazz 180nm SOI process. The ultimate goal for such application is to reach high performance and low cost, and between high performance and low power consumption design. This paper introduces the design of a 2.4GHz class E power amplifier and RF switch design. PA consists of cascade stage with negative capacitance. This power amplifier can transmit 16dBm output power to a 50Ω load. The performance of the power amplifier and switch meet the specification requirements of the desired.

KEYWORDS

Cascode, Negative Capacitance, Class E, Power amplifier, Healthcare, RF switch

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RESEARCH IN BIG DATA – AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Big data is a prominent term which characterizes the improvement and availability of data in all three formats like structure, unstructured and semi formats. Structure data is located in a fixed field of a record or file and it is present in the relational data bases and spreadsheets whereas an unstructured data file includes text and multimedia contents. The primary objective of this big data concept is to describe the extreme volume of data sets i.e. both structured and unstructured. It is further defined with three “V” dimensions namely Volume, Velocity and Variety, and two more “V” also added i.e. Value and Veracity. Volume denotes the size of data, Velocity depends upon the speed of the data processing, Variety is described with the types of the data, Value which derives the business value and Veracity describes about the quality of the data and data understandability. Nowadays, big data has become unique and preferred research areas in the field of computer science. Many open research problems are available in big data and good solutions also been proposed by the researchers even though there is a need for development of many new techniques and algorithms for big data analysis in order to get optimal solutions. In this paper, a detailed study about big data, its basic concepts, history, applications, technique, research issues and tools are discussed.

KEYWORDS:

Big data, Technologies, Visualization, Classification, Clustering

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